

**REPORT OF THE EVALUATION
OF DONCASTER ACTIVE
TRAVEL ALLIANCE
(DATA)**

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Executive summary

The Doncaster Active Travel Alliance (DATA) is a cross-departmental (service) partnership within the council, established to drive forward a coordinated and strategic approach to promoting active travel across Doncaster. It plays a key role in ensuring that active travel is not only promoted but sustained as a core element of the council's long-term vision for healthier, more resilient communities.

An evaluation was undertaken between April and August 2025, with the aim of examining DATA's collaborative approach to delivering its action plan and identify ways to improve future ways of working based on partners' experiences. Documents were reviewed, and in-depth semi-structured interviews conducted with 19 partners of DATA. This report presents the qualitative evaluation and is structured around four broad themes: (a) Understanding of purpose and goals, (b) Role definition and alignment, (c) Partnership successes and strengths (d) Sustainability and future working. Subthemes also emerged within these themes and are detailed in the report.

Partners revealed that the alliance has recorded positive progress over the years, attributed to collective support and teamwork. Key achievements include positive collaboration that influenced decisions, and opportunities created for learning, knowledge exchange, resource sharing, and capacity building. However, the evaluation also identified areas requiring further attention, one of which is the need for clearer role definitions and assigned responsibilities across partners. Additionally, there was a call for more inclusive and consistent engagement. Partners emphasised the importance of redefining the shared purpose, developing a structured strategy, and clearly outlining how they can support one another moving forward. Future strategies and ideas to enhance collaboration and future working were also suggested and detailed in the recommendations. Overall, there was a general sense of optimism regarding the progress and sustainability of DATA.

1.0 Background

The Doncaster Active Travel Alliance (DATA) is a strategic partnership that brings together representatives from key service areas across the council to champion and advance active travel (namely walking, wheeling and cycling) across the borough. The alliance serves as a central platform for aligning efforts, sharing expertise, coordinating initiatives that support healthier modes of transport and collectively delivering on the council's active travel priorities. It serves as a mechanism for strengthening internal collaboration, ensuring that active travel is considered across relevant policies, programmes, and service delivery. Through the development and implementation of a shared action plan, the alliance supports:

- Embedding active travel considerations into wider council strategies and planning processes.
- Behaviour changes through targeted engagement, infrastructure improvements, and policy development.
- Infrastructure developments that enhance accessibility, safety, and connectivity.
- Monitoring to track progress, inform decision-making, and demonstrate impact of active travel initiatives.

By fostering integrated working, the alliance contributes to broader council objectives, such as public health improvement, environmental sustainability, and inclusive mobility. It plays a key role in shaping and implementing a shared action plan, ensuring that projects are not only well-coordinated but also responsive to local needs and opportunities. This long-standing alliance brings together diverse partners who collaborate on aligned priorities and coordinated actions to drive meaningful change. While the partnership has delivered value, there is a growing need to reflect on its current ways of working to ensure continued relevance and impact.

2.0 Aim

The aim of the evaluation was to explore partners' perceptions of the impact of DATA's collaborative approach to delivering its active travel action plan, and to understand how future ways of working could be improved.

2.1 Specific objectives

1. Explore and understand how partners perceive the purpose of DATA and interpret their individual roles and contributions within it.
2. Explore partners' perceptions of how their involvement in DATA influences their roles and service areas.
3. Explore partners' reflections on collaborative working, including successes, challenges, and future considerations.

3.0 Method

In-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted between April and August 2025. A document review was also conducted on workshop notes and minutes from previous DATA meetings.

3.1 Recruitment of participants

All DATA partners were contacted via email and invited to participate in the interviews. Each email included an information sheet (detailing the purpose of the evaluation) and a consent form. 19 partners responded, provided their consent via email, and subsequently participated in the interviews.

3.2 Data collection and management

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with partners to allow for a flexible and in-depth exploration of their perspectives on the topics discussed. The interviews were guided by a topic framework aligned with the evaluation objectives.

Interviews were held via Microsoft Teams which lasted between 30 to 60 minutes. Each session was facilitated by a researcher, allowing for a detailed exploration of participants' experiences and perspectives. The researcher took notes throughout, capturing key reflections and insights. Recordings of the interviews were stored on Microsoft Teams for a maximum of 60 days before being permanently deleted. To ensure confidentiality, all identifying information were removed from the data. Responses (quotes) for partners included in this report have been fully anonymised.

3.3 Data Analysis

Interview recordings were transcribed verbatim to ensure accuracy and preserve the richness of the data. An inductive approach was employed to analyse the data, aiming to uncover deeper insights and patterns. Data coding and thematic development were carried out. The analysis followed Braun and Clarke's (2012) six-phase framework for Thematic Analysis. Through this process, the data was coded and organised into key themes and subthemes as they emerged during analysis.

4.0 Findings

The findings of this report are organised into thematic sections that align with the evaluation objectives. Each section explores specific theme and subthemes that emerged from the data and are presented separately for clarity. However, there are some areas of overlap. Based on the objectives, four key themes emerged with clearly defined sub-themes as reported below. Participants' responses are presented in italics and identified using codes P1 to P19.

4.1 Understanding of purpose and goals

Partners frequently reflected on DATA, as a group that unites them around a shared strategic vision. They expressed a broad awareness of the alliance, highlighting its collective vision and holistic approach to promoting active travel (walking, wheeling and cycling). Some partners also referenced DATA's strategic alignment with broader public health goals. Furthermore, the alliance was described as one that fosters cross-team working and mutual understanding, factors perceived as essential for integrated planning and effective partnership. Below are two sub-themes that highlighted partner's perspectives.

4.1.1 Shared sense of purpose

Partners commonly described DATA as a collaborative group united by a shared purpose, which they perceived has helped maintain its focus and direction over the years. The alliance was broadly recognized as having a "shared mission" to improve active travel. This sense of collective intent is reflected in these responses:

"It's kind of collaboration that comes together to kind of share resources, share experience, share best practice, but ultimately with that objective of getting more people walking, wheeling and cycling. (P7)"

"it's sort of drawing all those groups together with a shared interest in active travel so that we've got like an understanding in a way of working so that we're all sort of putting in the same direction rather than in different directions, which we have done in the past" (P6).

"just that space to discuss active travel in general so that ideas can come about from different stakeholders coming together in that capacity and having sort of that space to co-design, look at different things that might be useful moving forward" (P12).

Partners noted that DATA is ***"a greater sum of individual parts,"*** highlighting the value placed on joint efforts. However, while the capability to achieve its overall objective was acknowledged, partners

expressed the need to reaffirm purpose: revisit and clarify goals and strategies. This was perceived as essential not only for alignment across partners but also for motivation and sustained involvement.

“So in my view, I think it would be good to refresh sort of like what our shared targets are and our ambitions out of it, what the key strategy is there. (P8)”

“A reminder of what shared goals are and what we are working towards. (P1)”

“when I first joined.... It was clear what the actions were coming out of that meeting, it was clear what our vision was and what journey of travel we were all taking. So that needs to be strengthened” revising that purpose, but it could be the thing that motivates and drives other people to be involved” (P18).

“You know they go around, and everybody gives you update, but it's what the overall goal is. If it can be a bit more sort of focus on that. And then I would imagine the people that maybe not as active would then know what specific areas people are trying to drill down into, and maybe it's just a case that they're not quite sure what's required of them(P3).

These reflections suggest that while the alliance was perceived as collaborative, there is a need to strengthen shared understanding and renew its motivating purpose.

4.1.2 Value recognition

Several partners highlighted the value of bringing together stakeholders involved in active travel, noting that it enables resource pooling, strengthens support for initiatives, and reduces duplication of projects. The alliance was also noted as a platform for collaboration, knowledge sharing, and mutual support. This perception was consistent across most partners, highlighting the relevance of DATA as reflected in these quotes:

“Yeah, this's how I see it. I see there's a lot of people from different sort of background teams all coming together and sort of liaising to see we can help each other” (P5).

“It is kind of a forum that allows us to ensure strategic alignment. We're not duplicating work. we're not missing any work streams. So yeah, it's where everybody can come together and make sure that there's some sense of logic behind our actions” (P18).

There was also an identification of DATA's broader value, not only in terms of tangible actions like infrastructure and projects, but also in shaping the narrative and clarifying the purpose behind the work: ***“You know, so we're kind of adding value and creating the story around it. It's not just what we're doing, it's why we're doing it and it's those people that it's impacting on.” (P7).***

Despite DATA's recognised value, some partners felt its role in supporting individual teamwork is sometimes not clearly defined or fully utilised as noted in these quotes:

“And I feel like some people don't always see this group as being there to really help and support in their work, so when they are doing work, I don't feel like they think, right? How can this feed into data and how can they help deliver this. And maybe that's where we're kind of going wrong” (P3).

“don't really know what members want out of it” (workshop notes).

These responses further highlight the need for greater clarity around DATA's purpose in supporting the practical needs of all teams.

4.2 Role definition and alignment

Partners described their roles in terms of what they bring to the table, for example, skills, expertise, capacity, and resources, and also emphasised the importance of relying on one another. There was a shared view among partners that collaboration involves more than fulfilling individual roles; it requires working together in ways that maximise collective strengths and contribute to a shared purpose.

4.2.1 Clarity of role and contribution

Responses from partners reflected a collaborative mindset, with individual contributions seen as integral to a larger, interconnected system. Some partners described their roles not only in terms of delivering service-specific tasks but also in how they contribute strategically to the broader aims of DATA. There was an understanding of the importance of aligning roles with those of others to enhance collective impact, add value and strengthen more meaningful connections:

“So, I suppose my role from the service area is more of a kind of informing people of what we're doing and trying to get them to add value.” (P7)

“So, it's working with the other members to see how our role fits and how we can link in with other areas and support work (P3).

However, there were few perceptions that not all partners may have a clear sense of how their roles connect to the broader team or collective goal as indicated in the responses below:

“I think sometimes there can be an assumption that everyone knows, understands their role and what they're doing there and kind of links to that wider I suppose vision for that we all have (P14).

“I don't feel like it's my meeting. So, it's like, yeah, I am sort of like quite happy to just sort of contribute my update and sort of listen and find out what's going on (P5).

This was perceived to reflect a sense of detachment, which may have influenced the level of participation: ***“Some probably engage more whereas I think some others see it as possibly an add on to the role” (P10).***

A partner noted the need of re-engaging colleagues and clarifying how individual roles align within the wider collaborative effort: ***“So, I think we're now at a time where we've got an opportunity to bring colleagues in and to re-establish how our role all fits together and how we can best work together” (P14).*** This was seen as a way to enhance partnership working and renew a shared sense of purpose.

Responses from partners highlight the value of improving how roles are understood and coordinated, to support more focused and purposeful ways of working. This could also strengthen shared understanding and encourage broader participation.

4.3 Partnership successes and strengths

Partners highlighted the benefits of collaboration and reflected on the progress made through collective efforts. Below are four sub-themes that highlighted partner's perspectives.

4.3.1 Collaborative value

There was a shared perception that DATA has played a productive role over the years, helping to close gaps between teams and strengthen joint working which has been reflected in recorded progress over time:

“Through DATA we've been able to come together, we've created projects together or we've assisted each other on things that maybe have got a strict deadline, and you know there's more manpower required to get those things done. So, there's that good collaboration happening” (P10).

“We have had big achievements working collaboratively” (P6).

One partner further illustrated the significance of the alliance, describing it as: ***“a model for collaborative work internally within Doncaster Council” (P8)***, reflecting its value as a shared platform that supports joint decision-making and cross-team engagement.

Another partner identified the alliance as: ***“a kind of a forum that has allowed us to ensure purposeful alignment” (P18).***

The alliance was also described as a strategic partnership and recognised for its contribution to delivery: ***“We're recognised as an example of best practise in terms of how we work across council on this active travel agenda to get delivery and how it's enabled delivery” (P7).***

Partners also noted that having the right team members working together has been beneficial and contributed to DATA's progress. This has influenced and facilitated the processes behind schemes and projects as noted in these quotes:

"having some partners in DATA has allowed us to move forward by having that person that's really advocating, we've been able to move forward quicker and in a more responsive manner than other local authorities... Also since covid and coming together as a group, we were able to help shape those initiatives, so the behaviour change element due to teams' work, you know we were able to influence that. So, I think that's a big achievement" (P12).

"I think it allows us to kind of get a buy in from a lot of internal stakeholders quite early on in scheme development" (P7).

However, it was perceived that collaboration still needed to be further strengthened, encouraging more joint working across all teams as indicated in these quotes:

"I don't think we've got enough collaboration across some teams (P17).

"I guess collaboration with people across some teams, I think probably might need a little bit of work maybe" (P14).

Generally, partners highlighted that some of the key benefits of the collaborative work were evident in the successful delivery of certain local plan policies, including coordinated and successful funding bids.

4.3.2 Quality of relationship

Partners acknowledged that the alliance has helped build connections, making colleagues more accessible and approachable, and fostering positive working relationships and mutual support, as reflected in these quotes:

"When I started in my role years ago, that was one of my first meetings where I came into contact with a particular team. So, I think it's, it's helped relationship building there definitely (P10).

"Where I'm not able to solve a certain issue on my own and then when I discuss it with my team members, they know someone from data who would be able to help me out and I think that's what is really helpful" (P9).

One partner noted that: ***"we've built strong relationships that go beyond formal meetings."*** (P4).

The relationship-built overtime was well acknowledged and anticipated to remain valuable in the long term: ***“And you do get that opportunity to build relationships, and some things might come a bit in the future, I think it is important and it's a really nice aspect to it” (P1).***

The opportunity to build relationships through the alliance was seen as valuable, with the involvement of partners from different teams contributing positively to the experience.

4.3.3 Cross-team learning

Partners described DATA as a valuable platform for shared learning across teams and for gaining insight into each other's work. Discussions during meetings were considered relevant and useful even in the context of individual roles:

“So, there's been some learning I've taken from the data sessions that I've been able to use to improve my understanding of what the team does” (P10).

“Some key Information shared during meeting, that's really important to my job and which is not something I would have picked up outside of data” (P5).

Furthermore, a common perception across partners was that DATA has greatly enhanced knowledge and awareness of ongoing and potential active travel schemes/projects. It was also noted that involvement in DATA has deepened understanding and contributed to a more informed approach to work as reflected by these partners:

“DATA has improved my insights in shaping some of the we've work done...it also allows me to know of new initiatives and things like that are coming forward that one can engage with communities around that (P11).

“Interacting with a particular team gave me insight on a task” (P9).

Engagement in DATA created space for reflection and learning, enabling individuals to connect with broader strategic thinking in ways that may influence how roles are understood and approached. As highlighted in the quote below, the experience was perceived as adding value to the work and offering a wider perspective: ***“I take on board some of the strategic priorities from DATA, so it definitely enhances my role and also gives me a different viewpoint” (P18).***

The alliance was also perceived as a space that fosters confidence, enabling members to take initiative and act decisively. One partner noted that: ***“I am often able to make bold brave decisions and supported by DATA” (Workshop notes).***

Most partners highlighted the value of diverse expertise across the alliance. One partner shared how collaboration has prompted a shift in how success could be assessed, moving from solely tracking immediate actions to considering broader effects and long-term value: ***“I think obviously kind of working with public health. I think it allows us to be kind of more outcome focused than outputs terms of you know (P7).***

Another noted that being part of the alliance prompted more focused reflection about future priorities and how to assess progress, highlighting an aspect that had previously been outside the usual scope of work: ***“I think data has definitely made me give more consideration to that future planning and evaluation and it's not necessarily my strong point (P8).***

Overall, it was noted that greater learning and support could be achieved if all partners effectively leveraged the diverse expertise available across teams.

4.3.4 Resourceful network

The alliance was viewed as a space that enables pulling resources together including tools, knowledge, expertise and opportunities in ways that support shared learning and collaborative action. One participant described how the alliance creates a responsive environment for sharing projects/initiatives that could lead to wider engagement: ***“I definitely feel 100%, there is a space that if something comes up, I can share that, and you know, it might be a brand-new project that we can all get involved in with our perspectives. It's a fantastic space to share those things” (P11).***

Another partner also reiterated that: ***“Pulling resources collectively as an alliance has allowed and helped us to do more than we could individually” (P6).***

"The relevance and usefulness of the knowledge shared was also acknowledged by this partner, who stated: ***“I've learned about funding streams and tools I wouldn't have known about otherwise” (P1).***

Some partners noted that having the right connections through the DATA's network helped foster meaningful involvement with relevant groups as reflected in these quotes:

“The partners I've dealt with have always been quite proactive. They've been aware—like, say, if I've asked for a particular lead for a school—they've been really forthcoming with that information.” (P19)

“So we did support some team members by giving them details of community groups that they could contact, and they did use some of those community groups to set up the engagement meetings. And then hearing from them at the meeting how one has progressed and two others are progressing is great.” (P4)

The alliance was perceived to be instrumental in strengthening collaboration, enabling partners to leverage each other's expertise, knowledge, and networks for greater collective impact.

4.4 Sustainability and future working

Partners' responses reflect how the alliance could be further improved. A key insight that emerged was the need for more inclusive engagement, which was perceived as a foundation for sustainable and forward-thinking practice. Partners also highlighted that engagement should be guided by clearly defined goals, actions, and responsibilities, as this could reduce siloed working and promote shared ownership. Most partners emphasised that meetings **"should always translate into actions."** Below are five subthemes that highlights partners views on future ways of working.

4.4.1 Active and inclusive engagement

The need for more platforms to facilitate increased interaction, connection, and growth among partners emerged strongly from the responses. These opportunities were described as ones that can "invigorate people", encouraging them to contribute and to attend meetings more actively.

Partners felt that avenues should be created to work together on projects or initiatives, as this could be helpful and encourage active participation, as reflected in the following quotes:

"might be great to do a bit of an engagement, not tasks, but sort of activity and where maybe there is a project coming up. So it is a real life example and we maybe sit down and go through how. So, actually, who is it we need to engage with? how we're going to do it, when it's going to happen, things like that. So I think that'd be great. And then almost like a plan that you can pick up and copy if it's a similar project" (P11).

I think maybe getting people to work together in the meetings and I think that might be quite useful, particularly to hear from some of the ones who don't necessarily share much information "(P10).

This was further reflected in other responses, which indicated that a unified approach to topics or areas of work could be more valuable, encouraging joint working and helping to bring together diverse perspectives:

"For example it's like picking one particular community and how we approach increasing active travel in that community and everybody looking at that from their own perspectives rather than getting only an update. Sort of people are not finding it as productive as what it could be or was. (P3)

“but maybe instead of having it as a bulletin rather say right this is happening? How can we all get involved in it? Who's best placed to support. (P13)

“possibly identify some areas of focus that meets a variety of objectives going forward and that other people can work together on” (P1).

It was felt that some partner's contributions were more visible due to the direct relevance of DATA's goals to their roles, while others were possibly less engaged due to a perceived lack of alignment as highlighted in this quote: ***“there's definitely people who are more vocal and have more to say because their work looks in a lot more detail than other teams, which probably should still be quite high on the importance list. Again, it's just on that priority list of where it sits for other people” (P8).***

Reviewing the action plan was viewed as a potential way to promote more collaborative working, as it could allow for better alignment with the workstreams of all partners. It was also perceived that it could support better engagement from less active partners and promote a clearer understanding of how individual roles contribute:

“A broader action plan that will give everyone an opportunity to contribute and collaborate If that is something that is created for the whole of the group and some time to look at the action plan. We all need a kind of a shared vision of what needs to happen. So, I think enabling people to understand better why they're there would help”. (P12).

“We kind of get it to be more engaging, look at the action plans and you look at what we are working on, where do you think you fit into this. So I think it's about how we inject that kind of passion back into it” (P7).

“And I think its coming down to understanding what we are doing, how it aligns and being able to shape that vision with them can actually lead people to being a bit more engaged” (P18).

The responses from partners indicate a shared view that coordinated, collaborative efforts across different areas of work and teams could contribute to more meaningful impacts, including greater participation. They also reflect a broader need to revisit current strategies and co-develop more integrated approaches.

4.4.2 Strengthening ownership and accountability

Partners consistently highlighted the importance of creating more structured, smaller groups to enhance collaboration, engagement, and ownership. They felt that such spaces would enable individuals with relevant expertise and experience to connect more meaningfully, share knowledge,

and contribute more effectively to specific projects or initiatives. The responses shared below reflect partners' perceptions on how the alliance could be improved:

“like having the development of subgroups where it's more targeted with certain areas where they can overlap a lot more. So it'll provide an opportunity for understanding what a topic is and who's best to be part and parcel of it, and then create that subgroup from that” (P15).

“Like little subgroups I think would work quite well” (P9).

“Having smaller teams within DATA and then people working together (P1).

The absence of subgroups was also seen as a missed opportunity for more targeted support as reflected in this quote: ***“We don't get to do those little subgroups, and I feel like that would really benefit people that are working on certain projects to have those people that have got experience and knowledge in certain areas to really work together” (P2).***

In addition, the sub-groups were perceived as a way to foster a stronger sense of responsibility: ***“we could have little subgroups that can work together on certain pieces of work that can meet more regularly, really working together on that stuff. Some might think that it's other teams responsibility than theirs, so don't always give the same level of time and effort towards it when actually it's part of everybody's work and we should all equally” (P2).***

Partners identified the need to clarify responsibilities, and set clear expectations, including how progress will be assessed. Shared responsibilities were seen as a way to reduce “silo working” and encourage greater commitment.

“I think we probably needed to make sure that we update that action plan and give people kind of key roles and responsibilities, where people have got, you know, people kind of are responsible within that and talk about how we're going to be measuring success (P7).

“And I think what could work is to just have a bit more actions for everyone in those meetings (P18).

One partner, however, felt that active commitment to the action plan currently rests with only a few teams. This limited sense of responsibility was perceived to hinder wider engagement, suggesting the need to explore ways to improve ownership: ***“I would say I don't think there's necessarily a sense of ownership of the action plan like in data as a whole. I think it feels, though it does sit with one or two teams that are part of that group. So whether there's potential to look at how that could be improved (P10).***

The need to document or maintain a clear record of partners working together on actions was perceived as important. It was felt that this could support more balanced participation, enhance

understanding of the significance of joint efforts, and aid in tracking progress, as reflected in the following quote: ***“we can have some kind of log where people note what they're working together on. If you really want to evaluate the value of that collaboration and the connections because of data, we probably need to start just logging it as we go. So there could always be an opportunity for 5 minutes and everyone just updates it” (P1).***

Partner responses reveal the importance of a strengthened inclusive approach, in which roles and responsibilities are clearly defined, communicated, and understood across the group to support transparency, accountability, and effective collaboration.

4.4.3 Interactive design for engagements

Partners emphasised the need for meetings to be more engaging and participatory, expressing their views on how to improve both the structure and agenda, as outlined below.

4.4.3.1 Purposeful meeting structure

Most partners highlighted that meetings should move beyond simply providing updates, with a stronger focus on actively driving activities forward. They expressed a desire for a more action-oriented format that will support more learning and practical problem-solving. Creating an environment that fosters discussions, and collaborative planning was generally emphasised:

One partner noted that the meeting: ***“needs to be more of like what the issues are. How can we work together to help solve them rather than kind of coming and going, we've delivered. Have 15 minutes to present a picture of what teams are working on at the moment to then feed into data, this is what problems we've got or like good examples and best practice ... Where can we input? What resource do you need” (P7).***

A more reflective and structured approach to updates was suggested by another partner, that focuses on sharing lessons learned, discussing challenges, and collaboratively exploring ways forward across projects and initiatives: ***“asking people to include what challenges are you facing? are there any asks from the group? Something like that to be included in every update. Then in a bit of a quadrangle of what's happened, 3 good learning points, any challenges, any areas of risk or something like that. What's next? I think it creates more of an environment where everyone feels comfortable to share challenges and they know that you're automatically going to get some suggestions. Yeah. I think that would create more of a learning and a collaborative environment and you then getting something for your work as well” (P1).*** The need to include future plans, outputs, and outcomes in the team updates were also noted.

Responses also suggested strengthening meeting formats to better support openness, peer support, and active contribution: ***“Yeah, we need to make sure that everyone's voice is heard. we're updating each other regularly on how things are going, how things are not going. Is there any suggestions to improve this? Because I could have been doing a role for some time now completely wrong. Someone could have input something which would have supported me earlier, and then I would have been far greater at the job, far more efficient it works, you know, it works the same for everyone. Really, we could all have input into each other's roles to an extent and help each other during meetings” (P19)***

Reflecting on those who are less active another partner noted: ***“And I'd say if we give them that time and opportunity to ask us for help and support on certain things, then it might make it more appealing to them to attend because the meetings have been so regimented” (P2).***

Partners further pointed out that meetings should be less formal and more engaging, with space provided for focused input and idea-sharing. The value of a more dynamic format of meeting was echoed in these quotes:

“so sometimes it feels like quite a formal meeting with an agenda. I think sometimes it could be more of a workshop and focus on one particular theme that links into everybody's roles. Another is maybe looking at more of that workshop style with something a bit more interactive that might help get everyone talking and become a bit more comfortable (P10).

“So it will could also be around having little workshops and coming together and getting people's ideas on a project, scheme or any area of focus (P1).

“I think that we have had a workshop session that was held and was really good and worked well. Such sessions would be great” (P15).

“looking at like the workshop style kind of getting people active because it's a long meeting and you just kind of sat (P18). These formats were perceived to make meetings more purposeful and supportive.

Suggestions also emerged around introducing formats such as spotlight sessions or presentations across teams which could be rotated (workshop notes). These were perceived as valuable for encouraging shared learning and generating new ideas. A previous presentation was especially relevant, as reflected in the following quote:

“last time there was a presentation around The WWC investment plan, just to see those numbers on the screen. like how much cycling delivery is being done, it then made me think right how they got them numbers, I need to speak to for some tips on how to get people cycling. So I suppose if

that presentation had not been shared it might not have gone off and then that's led to a meeting and some ideas and a joint meeting put in place" (P1).

There was also an interest in using the meetings as a space to explore specific topics in greater depth, with the potential to strengthen knowledge and build capacity, as reflected in these quotes:

"It'd be great to see included a bit of discussions around engaging with residents around active travel. think it'd be great just to know, different teams and different people's perspectives on how they engage with people and how they think's best to engage with residents around active travel" (P11).

"For me one thing that would be useful to know is sort of perspective ideas for investment (P7).

"understand the walk/wheel strategy: the creative detail behind it" (workshop notes).

It was generally acknowledged that partnership contributed to successes. However, the question ***"how are we doing?" (workshop notes)*** was highlighted as a key element to be discussed regularly in meetings by all partners, to ensure that progress is collectively monitored and achieved.

Meetings were felt to be dominated by representatives from certain teams, often involving repeated updates. One member reflected: ***"Sometimes it feels like a regular team meeting. I don't know maybe it could be smarter, slightly smaller, and you'd get more of a kind of strategic-level discussion" (P13).*** This reflects a perceived need to improve the structure and focus of meetings by reducing repetition and encouraging more purposeful discussion.

The current chairing arrangement was also perceived to concentrate influence within the teams represented by the co-chairs, which may limit broader group engagement. Rotating the co-chair or facilitation role was suggested as a way to include fresh perspectives, foster shared responsibility, and enhance engagement across the wider group as indicated in the quote: ***"I think at the moment, like how the meetings are co-chaired between x and x, it feels though a lot of the meeting and the group sits with those two teams. It might be like the co-chair changes each time, so there's somebody to kind of drive it overall, but somebody else has a bit more responsibility in those meetings. I think that might be helpful" (P10).***

Overall, partner's perceptions on meeting structures highlight the need for interactive designs which could support meaningful engagement and collective progress.

4.4.3.2 Strategic agenda design

While some partners valued having updates in the agenda due to the knowledge shared, there was an emphasis on streamlining them to save time. Few partners noted that sharing updates electronically

in advance should be considered, to allow for review and input. This was felt could allow prioritising agenda items that promote dialogue and joint problem-solving.

A partner highlighted the limitations of a tightly structured agenda and proposed blending updates with other focused discussions: ***“instead of just having it as bullet like update session, have each session kind of themed on a certain piece of work. And that's not to mean that they can't do updates afterwards, but that could be a part of it. So, people are aware, I'm pretty sure the same session can be blended. The agenda is very regimented, so I don't think that helps” (P13).***

Other partners also shared their views around the focus of the agenda on specific team topics, to enable more targeted discussions and cross-team collaboration as reflected in these quotes:

“So maybe having a different team at each meeting would be great” (P4)

“And I think it needs to maybe like focus. So each meeting would focus on a different team. It needs to be more about collaboration and problem solving, rather than information and update” (P7).

“maybe having key team at each one” (P3).

In addition, it was noted that holding team-focused meetings could also create space for deeper exploration of each team's work, generate cross-team insights, and highlight its relevance to other areas as indicated in this quote: ***“maybe we need to have a focus on the different stakeholders' areas of work. And that's what that meeting is going to talk about for the full time that were there, you know, we're going to come together and for example. That meeting is going to be all about air quality, and we're going to think about, you know, air quality in relation to planning, active travel etc. What is it that we all need to have an involvement in? What is it that we potentially can go away and think about for that team area and have a deep dive maybe on that (P10).***

The importance of incorporating agenda items that stimulate creative thinking and meaningful contributions also emerged. Suggestions included prompts such as ***“What do you need from meetings?”*** and ***“How best can we collaborate?” (workshop notes)***, which were seen as ways to encourage reflection, and dialogue among partners.

Co-designing future meeting agendas was also recognised as a valuable way to reflect partners' ideas, contributions, and priorities. One partner suggested: ***“reaching out to members and asking if there's anything that they could do you know, is there anything that you'd like to have 10 minutes for in the agenda (P18).***

The approach to agenda design, as reflected in partners' responses, was perceived as having the potential to facilitate more active and meaningful participation.

4.4.4 Coordinated communication planning

Partners noted the need for a more joined-up approach to promoting active travel schemes and initiatives, both within the council and the public. It was suggested that leveraging on events such as Walking Month, Road Safety Week and others could serve as avenues to raise awareness. Partners also pointed out that a perceived lack of awareness of these initiatives may be limiting their use, also highlighting the importance of identifying and addressing the reasons behind low usage:

“And I don't think everybody around the table or council even uses the facilities, so doesn't have that knowledge and awareness of it. It's not just like sort of photographs where we've done this, it's actually getting people using it. And capturing those review of why they're not using it. I don't know whether anymore could be done about cycling in the borough in terms of the communications or advertisements you know, where they're going, what they're doing, so, getting it out there that this has been laid and it's for the residents' benefits (P3).

“but we need a better representation from the Central Commons team” (P14).

With reference to wider consultations on an infrastructure a partner noted that: ***“as a resident, I found out that there was some public consultation on a cycle path almost outside my house by Facebook. I sit on DATA and I found out publicly. I think more could be put on the agenda so that in terms of links to current like sort of developments. Like when we've got plans in place so that they're shared more with the group” (P3).***

The need for improved and earlier communication around ongoing and future project plans across the team was highlighted. It was felt that emphasising the importance of all teams sharing such plans could encourage more collective support and potentially contribute to progress, as reflected in the following quotes.:

“giving people plenty of notice to say this is what we're looking to do, you know, just letting you know also, more than happy for you to help with whatever. Just drop us an e-mail or get in touch with how you think you can help “(P11).

“Most times by the time they update us on what's happening, it's too late. we've missed out and they've missed out on working with those people that probably have got the skills and the knowledge to help and support” (P2).

“Sometimes you’re kind of like, oh, did you get this and this permission for that or have you consulted with that, do you know what I mean? So it’s kind of like sometimes I feel that I’m kind of like on the back of that role, and not really in with it, if that makes sense. So, some of the projects xxx might impact on something else or persons that might need to be aware of early (P3).

Across most partners, the importance of communicating regular, consistent meetings scheduled well in advance was widely acknowledged. New partners in particular, who had previously struggled to attend, emphasised the value of early notice, as this could help them better prioritise their work:

“meetings should be booked in there early, I can plan in advance and move mine to a different time or something. So that’d be a big help for me (P4).

“Please book meetings way ahead of time so its known earlier and we can create time” (P16).

“I would like to be available for those meetings. Not like I don’t want to. I would like to, but I just need to know well in advance about that, (P17).

“I know people to have different meetings booked in, for example, but I think they should be saying like in a month’s time we’re setting this date. This is proposal. Can you please block your diary out in advance now? And then there’s no reason for anyone to be cancelling it. And then we know when that meetings come in, we’ve definitely got time in diary” (P19).

The discontinuation of online meetings without communication or input from all involved was perceived as inappropriate, highlighting the importance of inclusive decision-making. It was suggested by few partners that hybrid meeting options should be considered where possible.

Overall, partners highlighted that effective communication is key for future collaboration and progress.

4.4.5 Broader collaborative network

Partners feedback highlighted a strong consensus around the value of re-engaging certain service areas that have either become less active or have not been involved. Enforcement, Street Scene, Development Planning, Highways, Engineering, Communication and School Crossing Patrol were areas frequently mentioned as having important contributions to make, with their involvement seen as integral to the success of the alliance. Where engagement was lacking, it was perceived that this may be due, in part, to the need for support or encouragement from service leads. A partner noted: ***“some other teams not as great with the collaboration, so then that causes a little bit of blockage. Feel it depend on who’s at the head of their service” (P13).***

The importance of strengthening community engagement in projects was also highlighted, as reflected in the following quotes:

“I'd say the only part of data that I'd say could be improved is moving beyond the infrastructure to the engagement side of things, because we're doing master plans and we're kind of co creating with communities. What I'd like to see more, though it's a key message coming out now from DATA is that kind of co-creation with people, not just putting things in place for people. (P18).

“But I think there's some collaborative working to be done with the outside world and not just as Council officers coming together. like there could be a little bit more collaboration with users and not just kind of like sort of that sometimes is seen to be a group of people around the table making decisions” (P3).

There was a recognition that building stronger connections and engaging in more extensive consultations could help shape infrastructure in ways that are more relevant and responsive to local needs. This perspective is captured in the following quote: ***“a little bit more collaboration with developers and what's happening in an area, as there could be a developer in the area that could provide that collaboration with that facility. We need to be aware of what applications we've got in where and whether we can do some collaboration with developers. Some things are done silo and it's kind of not the greatest of achievements to put something in silo and then somebody else tear it up to be able to do something else. Now I think we should choose areas of significance to put facilities in for cycling, walking, wheeling. I think we need to be more aware of what developments are happening in the area as well as just the deficiency of what they've got” (P3).***

The presence of the right team partners, who have relevant knowledge and insight into the alliance's work, at meetings was seen as important for enabling meaningful and productive discussions, as illustrated in the following quote: ***“its important that different teams are not just represented in the room, but by the right people as well. So that you don't end up with somebody who's not very operational in an operational meeting and I think that'd be useful, particularly when we're trying to explain to other people what data is and how it fits in with everything else” (P10).***

Overall, there was an understanding of the value of strengthening connections and working more collaboratively.

5.0 Recommendations

The following recommendations were informed by partners' reflections, shared experiences, and suggestions. They are intended to strengthen the collaborative delivery of active travel initiatives and support the overall progress of the alliance.

- The current action plan should be reviewed and revised, incorporating inputs from all partners to reflect evolving priorities and insights. This approach could support a shared understanding of the DATA's purpose, clarify individual roles, and strengthen alignment with overall goals.
- Roles and responsibilities should be assigned, where appropriate, to promote ownership and accountability. Consider establishing smaller working groups focused on specific projects or cross-cutting themes to help accelerate progress and strengthen collaboration across teams. An action log can also be created to support tracking of progress and recognition of successes.
- Interactive elements such as workshops or spotlight presentations should be incorporated into meetings. This approach could encourage more active participation and facilitate knowledge sharing among members.
- Restructuring meeting agendas to include specific team- or topic-focused discussions should be considered, as this could encourage more interaction and dialogue while streamlining the time spent on sharing updates. Updates should follow a structured format that includes not only ongoing projects and successes but also challenges, areas where support is needed, future projects or plans, outputs, outcomes, and timelines.
- Meetings should be scheduled on a consistent basis and communicated well in advance to support effective planning and encourage regular attendance. Meetings should also be action-oriented, concluding with clearly assigned tasks where relevant and agreed-upon timelines.
- There should be a more structured approach to monitoring progress. This could include timelines to track activities and outcomes, regular review points to reflect on what's working and where adjustments are needed, simple shared formats (e.g., action logs, progress summaries).

References

1. Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2012). Thematic analysis. In H. Cooper, P. M. Camic, D. L. Long, A. T. Panter, D. Rindskopf, & K. J. Sher (Eds.), *APA handbook of research methods in psychology, Vol. 2: Research designs: Quantitative, qualitative, neuropsychological, and biological* (pp. 57–71). Washington, DC: American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1037/13620-004>.